

ON THE DETERMINATION OF THE NON-LINEAR LONGITUDINAL MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF SHORT-FIBRE COMPOSITES BY A THREE-DIMENSIONAL FINITE ELEMENT PROCEDURE

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Previous finite element analyses of the mechanical behaviour of discontinuous-filament composites have essentially considered either only single-fibre models or plate-reinforced structures rather than three-dimensional multi-fibre array geometries. In this paper, a three-dimensional finite element procedure is reported for the prediction of the mechanical behaviour of a unidirectional short-fibre composite under uniaxial longitudinal loading. The boundary conditions appropriate to this problem are formulated in terms of constraint equations on the nodal displacement pattern.

The isoparametric compatible displacement model of the finite element method is utilized for this work. The bulk constituents are represented by 20-node rectangular prism elements while a 16-node rectangular interface element is used to represent the bond behaviour of the fibre-matrix interface. Non-linear behaviour is considered in terms of an elasto-plastic model, based on the von Mises yield criterion, for the solid components and of a debonding model for the interface. The latter allows two modes of failure due to delamination and to tangential slippage. The initial stress method is employed for the non-linear solution scheme.

Application of this approach is given to two finite element examples selected from the literature. The internal stresses and local non-linear behaviour are studied and the composite stress-strain curves are predicted. These examples demonstrate the type of differences to be observed from a fully three-dimensional finite element analysis of multi-array short-fibre composites as compared to two-dimensional treatments.

The procedures reported in this paper can be simply extended to other geometries, load cases and material characterizations.

INTRODUCTION

Considerable effort has been expended in the analysis of the elastic behaviour of unidirectional fibrous-reinforced composite materials [1]. As a result, it is now possible to adequately estimate the initial elastic constants of, and the elastic stress concentrations within, the composite. However, such analyses are valid only up to the applied composite stress at which the most stressed material region reaches the limit to its elastic behaviour. This applied stress level is typically only a fraction of that at which composite failure is macroscopically recognised due to the resulting stress re-distributions around these regions. Such limits to elastic behaviour may be due, for example, to plastic yielding of the matrix or to failure of the fibre-matrix interface. The analysis of such forms of non-linear behaviour necessitates the use of some rigorous numerical scheme with the finite element method being perhaps the most versatile available.

The earliest applications of the finite element method to non-linear composite analysis have been in the realm of the elasto-plastic behaviour of unidirectional continuous filament structures [2,3]. The consideration of discontinuous reinforcement is a more difficult task due to the very presence of the fibre ends. Owen et al [4] employed axisymmetric and plane strain models to examine several single-fibre and multiple-fibre systems under longitudinal loading. Although no attempt was made to predict the macroscopic response, their results indicate that the inclusion of neighbouring fibres retards the spread of plastic zones as compared to single-fibre models. Agarwal et al [5,6] employed an axisymmetric analysis for short-fibre composites under uniaxial longitudinal loading. Two models of fibre arrangement were considered: a row-and-column array and a symmetric-staggered array of overlapping fibres. They obtained predictions of the composite stress-strain curve and demonstrated the better reinforcement of the model with overlapping fibres.

Applications of the finite element to the study of interfacial bond failure in a composite system has received scant attention in the literature. Owen and Lyness [7] used a plane strain analysis and the initial stress method to investigate bond failure in a single-fibre model under longitudinal loading. They employed a special bond element for the fibre-matrix interface and allowed delamination and slippage failure modes. For the cases studied, shear failure occurred at the fibre end and propagated down the fibre sides with subsequent loss of fibre axial stress. Further, complete debonding finally resulted so that the composite could not be loaded beyond the elastic limit.

The above finite element analyses are not truly representative of three-dimensional multi-fibre array geometries: use of a plane strain formulation actually models the case of plate-reinforced structures while an axisymmetric analysis ignores a portion of the matrix material. In this paper, a three-dimensional finite element procedure is reported for the prediction of the mechanical behaviour of one class of unidirectional short-fibre composites under uniaxial longitudinal loading. The effects of matrix yielding and of interfacial bond failure are studied for two examples selected from the literature.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

The finite element process in displacement analysis and the isoparametric element concept are well-known [8] and will not be discussed here. The bulk constituents are considered to be isotropic and are represented by 20-node rectangular prism elements. The bond behaviour at the fibre-matrix interface is taken to be non-dilatant and mechanically isotropic in tangential directions. For finite element modelling, a special 16-node rectangular interface element, with zero thickness, was developed [9,10]; this element is similar to one presented by Nayak and Agarwala [11]. Note that both element types employ quadratic displacement fields.

The initial stress method for non-linear analysis is also well-established [8,12,13] and is based upon the elimination of residual forces. Such forces arise when non-linear behaviour of the material regions is encountered during the application of a load increment. These residuals are calculated from the difference between the true stress level, governed by the material non-linear constitutive laws, and that corresponding to the incremental elastic solution. Since these forces represent a measure of the error of the approximation, they are elastically re-distributed through-out the entire structure in an iterative manner. This process of stress transfer is continued, and the body allowed to deform within a load increment, until the full non-linear compatibility and equilibrium conditions are satisfied; in the present case, the process is terminated when the ratio of the norm of the residual forces to the norm of the applied forces is less than a pre-determined value RTEST. Implicit in this method are the assumptions of small strains and of linear-strain-displacement relationships.

The forms of non-linear behaviour considered in this paper will now be briefly discussed. Further details of the analysis and of the numerical schemes are given in Refs. 9 and 10.

Elastic-Plastic Model:

The basic steps in the expression of the equations of elasto-plastic theory into a form suitable for the finite element method are well-established and can be found, for example, in Refs. 8,12 and 13. For the present work, the plasticity analysis is based on the von-Mises yield criterion with the associated flow rule for the plastic strain increment. Note that the initial stress method in elasto-plastic analysis has been shown to be unconditionally convergent by Argyris and Scharpf [14].

Debonding Model:

Owing to the lack of constitutive debonding relations, the basic model of Owen and Lyness [7] was extended into three-dimensional space. The mechanical behaviour of an interfacial point is linear (elastic) until conditions appropriate to initial failure are obtained; the stress-strain state is defined with reference to a local co-ordinate system x',y',z' normal to and tangential to the interface at the point under consideration (Fig. 1a). This initial failure is defined in terms of delamination or tangential slippage. Thereafter, the mechanical behaviour may be linear or non-linear depending upon the current state of stress and of the normal strain.

Delamination can be simply accounted for by a non-negative limit ϵ_D' to the normal strain component,

$$\epsilon_z' > \epsilon_D' \geq 0 \quad (1)$$

If, within a strain change, delamination occurs, then the interfacial point can no longer support any load so that its stress state becomes zero. Such a failure condition is illustrated in Fig. 1b. Closure of the interfacial crack at some later stage can be allowed by reversing the first inequality sign in Eq. (1).

In analogy with the elasto-plastic analysis, tangential slippage is assumed to be governed by a slippage criterion of the form,

$$F'(\tau_{xz}', \tau_{yz}', \kappa') \equiv g'(\tau_{xz}', \tau_{yz}') - T'(\kappa') = 0 \quad (2)$$

where g' determines the shape of a slippage locus in shear stress (τ_{xz}', τ_{yz}') space; and T' is the effective shear stress derived from uniaxial mechanical tests as a function of a hardening parameter κ' which may be identified with the work dissipated in slippage.

For the present work, the function g' was taken to be,

$$g'(\tau_{xz}', \tau_{yz}') \equiv \bar{\tau}' = \{(\tau_{xz}')^2 + (\tau_{yz}')^2\}^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

(a) Interface Element.

(b) Delamination Model.

(c) Slippage Model.

(d) Failure Surface ($i=m, r, s$).

Fig. 1: Finite element model for imperfect fibre-matrix interface.

so that the slippage locus is that of a circle of radius $T'(\kappa')$. The values of $T'(\kappa')$ were considered to be governed by the following general relation,

$$T'(\kappa') \equiv \bar{\tau}_z^i = \begin{cases} C_i + \mu_i |\sigma_z^i|^n & ; \sigma_z^i < 0 \\ C_i & ; \sigma_z^i \geq 0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where $C_i \geq 0$ is a cohesion constant through which the effects of chemical or electrical bonding and of compressive residual stresses may be allowed;

$\mu_i \geq 0$ is a measure of the friction between the constituent surfaces;

$n \in [2/3, 1]$ allows the consideration of elastic, viscoelastic, or plastic interfacial slip [15]; and,

$i=m, r, s$ depends on the loading history (and replaces the parameter κ').

This relationship is illustrated in Fig. 1c. the subscript i can be interpreted in the following manner. Providing no delamination has occurred, the shear behaviour is elastic until the maximum shear strength $\bar{\tau}_m^i$ is exceeded; if delamination has occurred, then $\bar{\tau}_m^i$ replaces $\bar{\tau}_m^i$ after crack closure. Thereafter the shear stresses fall to a residual effective value $\bar{\tau}_r^i$. Accompanying this instantaneous stress drop, an equivalent increment of elastic shear strain has slipped and is thus converted into a slippage strain increment. Subsequent shear behaviour is linear until slippage is re-initiated at the static value $\bar{\tau}_m^i$. This behaviour represents a stick-slip mechanism observed in rod-disk tests for interfacial shear strength [16,17]. Of course, suitable variation of the parameters in Eq. (4) allows the consideration of other forms of non-linear behaviour, such as steady slippage ($\bar{\tau}_m^i = \bar{\tau}_r^i$) and a Mohr-Coulomb criterion ($n=1$; C_i, μ_i identical for all i).

Continuing the analogy with the elasto-plastic analysis enables one to simply determine the form of the unequilibrated stress essential for the calculation of the residual forces for the initial stress method.

The combination of these two modes of debonding can be visualized as a failure surface in stress space, Fig. 1d. A stress state outside the current envelope has no meaning while one inside the surface is in a state of elastic stress so that slippage has either yet to occur or has been arrested. For the general case of the stick-slip failure mechanism, the surface continuously expands to $\bar{\tau}'_s$ (or initially $\bar{\tau}'_m$) and then instantaneously contracts to $\bar{\tau}'_p$. Finally, it is to be noted that although delamination results in a loss of the initial shear failure mode ($\bar{\tau}'_m$) as well as of the shear stresses, the present model assumes no effect of initial and continuing shear failure on the delamination mode.

COMPOSITE ANALYSIS

A typical uni-directional fibrous-reinforced composite under microscopic examination reveals many variations in filament shape, cross-section, continuity, packing and collimation. This makes any mechanical analysis virtually impossible without prior idealization of the reinforcement geometry. Such homogenizing idealizations for continuous and discontinuous reinforcement are discussed in Ref. 9. For the problems reported in this paper, the fibres are assumed to pack in a row-and-column arrangement in the longitudinal direction with square packing in the transverse plane, Fig. 2. With isotropic or transversely isotropic constituent materials, such a structure may be macroscopically characterized as a square symmetric material with six independent elastic constants [18].

Fig. 2: Idealized geometry for unidirectional short-fibre composite.

Dimensions: $CF = b$ $AC = a$ $AB = a$

- I: any node on face ADFC
- J: any node on face ABC
- K: any node on face DEF
- L: any node on face ADEB
- P: any node on line CF
- Q: any node on line BE
- R: any node on face BEFC
excluding P, Q
- Y: independent node on face DEF
- Z: independent node on face ADEB

Fig. 3: Minimal repeat unit for uniaxial longitudinal loading.

Because of the assumed periodicity, a typical repeating unit, such as that indicated by the dashed lines in Fig. 2, can be isolated for detailed analysis. For the case of uniaxial longitudinal loading, the transverse geometry remains that of square packing. Thus the smallest fully informative repeat unit is the structure illustrated in Fig. 2 (solid lines) and Fig. 3. However, constraint conditions must be imposed on the five boundary planes of this repeat unit since symmetry requires that these planes retain their original orientations. For the discretized finite element problem, these constraint conditions may be expressed in terms of linear constraint equations on the nodal displacement pattern. With reference to Fig. 3, the finite element problem is then defined as follows,

$$\begin{array}{l} \text{applied} \\ \text{stress} \end{array} \quad \tilde{\sigma}_y = \frac{2F_{y,Y}}{a^2} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \text{resultant} \\ \text{strains} \end{array} \quad \tilde{\epsilon}_y = \frac{v_Y}{b} \quad \tilde{\epsilon}_x = \frac{u_B}{a} \quad \tilde{\epsilon}_z = \frac{w_Z}{a} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \text{fixed} \\ \text{boundary} \\ \text{conditions} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} u_I = 0 \\ u_P = 0 \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} v_J = 0 \\ w_P = 0 \end{array} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{array}{l} \text{boundary} \\ \text{constraint} \\ \text{equations} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} v_K = v_Y \\ u_Q = w_Z \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} w_L = w_Z \\ u_R = w_R \end{array} \quad (8)$$

where u_i, v_i, w_i are displacements in the x,y,z directions, respectively, for the appropriate node i;

$F_{y,Y}$ is the equivalent applied force in the y-direction for node Y;
and, the nodal displacements on the right-hand side of Eqs. (8) are considered independent in the analysis.

For the incorporation of linear constraint equations in finite element analysis, two basic approaches [19] are available: Lagrange multipliers, and condensation procedures. The former scheme is more elegant in terms of variational procedures and views the Lagrange multipliers as additional nodal forces for the maintenance of equilibrium subject to the constraint conditions. However, this approach expands the system of stiffness equations representing the behaviour of the structure. Further, the resulting equations can no longer be guaranteed positive definite, thus necessitating care in the selection of an appropriate equation solver. The condensation approach recognises the redundancy among the constrained variables and thus contracts the system of stiffness equations. This can yield considerable savings in computer storage and time requirements, particularly for large non-linear problems. Further, the resultant stiffness equations remain positive definite. This approach has been adopted for the present work and the solution algorithm is reported in Refs. 9 and 20. It should be noted that this algorithm is more general than the usual condensation scheme.

The constraint formulation of the boundary conditions appropriate to other composite geometries and load cases is discussed in Ref. 9. In the case of continuous reinforcement, good agreement has been obtained with existing elastic and elasto-plastic analyses [3,18,21].

ELASTO-PLASTIC EXAMPLE

The first problem considered is one studied by Agarwal et al [5,6]. The assumed composite geometry is illustrated in Fig. 4 together with the discretization (employing 84 rectangular elements). The composite dimensions equivalent to the axi-symmetric analysis [5,6] are the fibre aspect ratio (length to diameter) of 10 and the one fibre-radius nearest-neighbour separation in both the transverse and longitudinal directions. Thus the only difference is due to the three-dimensional

Fig. 4: Discretization for short-fibre composite with elasto-plastic matrix.

Fig. 5a: Effect of matrix yielding on stress-strain behaviour.

Fig. 5b: Effect of matrix yielding on longitudinal Poisson ratio.

Load Increment	Number of Iterations	$\bar{\sigma}_y$ MPa	(ksi)	$\bar{\epsilon}_y$ %	ν_{LT}
1	1	48.3	(7.000)	0.2455	0.2816
2	1	53.1	(7.700)	0.2700	0.2816
3	3	72.4	(10.500)	0.3802	0.2842
4	4	89.7	(13.000)	0.4887	0.2871
5	5	106.9	(15.500)	0.6041	0.2902
6	4	115.5	(16.750)	0.6642	0.2918
7	5	126.7	(18.375)	0.7464	0.2942
8	6	137.9	(20.000)	0.8343	0.2972
9	9	155.2	(22.500)	0.9809	0.3029
10	13	172.4	(25.000)	1.1449	0.3096
11	19	189.6	(27.500)	1.3350	0.3174
12	30	206.9	(30.000)	1.5681	0.3270

TABLE 1: NON-LINEAR RESPONSE OF SHORT-FIBRE COMPOSITE DUE TO MATRIX YIELDING

Fig. 6: Progression of plastic zone boundaries.

representation utilizing square packing of the fibres. This reduces the fibre volume from 42.4% for the axi-symmetric case to 34.9%. The constituent properties were taken as follows:

	<u>Fibre</u>	<u>Matrix</u>
Poisson Ratio	0.20	0.35
Young's Modulus (MPa)	81.38×10^3	2.76×10^3
(psi)	(11.80×10^6)	(0.40×10^6)
Yield Stress (MPa)	-	55.17
(ksi)	-	(8.00)
Yield Slope (kPa)	-	690.0
(psi)	-	(100.0)

The predicted tensile behaviour is reported in Table 1 and Fig. 4-5; for convergence, RTEST = 5×10^{-5} . The composite elastic modulus and initial yield stress were calculated to be 19.65×10^3 MPa (2.85×10^6 psi) and ~ 50.76 MPa (7.36 ksi) respectively. The former value is to be compared to 24.69×10^3 MPa (3.58×10^6 psi) as obtained by Agarwal et al [5,6] and reflects the effect of the included matrix material. Although not reported by these authors, it would appear from Fig. 5a that the calculated composite initial yield stress is of a similar order of magnitude. The results in Fig. 5b are particularly interesting. The von Mises yield criterion implies a Poisson ratio of 0.5 for the plastic component which may be viewed as a third phase in the composite system. Thus the increasing composite longitudinal Poisson ratio suggests a growing amount of yielded matrix and this is indeed the case as will be shown shortly.

The catastrophic failure predicted by the axi-symmetric approach was not observed, even for an applied load of almost double the final value obtained by Agarwal et al [5,6]. That the composite non-linearity is accelerating is indicated by the number of iterations per load increment in Table 1 and the curves in Fig. 5. However, the applied load corresponding to any suspected catastrophic failure may be much higher than the final load of 30 ksi considered in the present study.

Examination of the matrix elastic stress pattern reveals the existence of high triaxial stress states in the gap between collinear fibres and in the included matrix. The former observation is due to the restraining influence of the fibre end whilst the latter reflects the influence of adjacent fibres in the simulated multi-fibre composite. Near the fibre edge, large values of the shear components are observed with the normal stresses greatly reduced in magnitude. These features of the matrix stress pattern can be expected to influence the progression of matrix yielding for applied loads beyond the initial composite yield stress.

Fig. 6 shows the progress of plastic zone boundaries for increasing composite load; the boundary numbers correspond to the applied load increments in Table 1. Initial yielding is axi-symmetric to an applied load of approximately 90 MPa (13 ksi). Thereafter, yielding is greatly influenced by the presence of the included matrix and the simulated multi-fibre structure. Away from the cylindrical fibre surface, yielding generally arises from the disparity between the normal stress components. At this surface, a large shear component is involved. Thus, the region of no yield near the fibre end is associated with a high nearly-hydrostatic stress state; it is interesting to note that Agarwal et al [5,6] also observed a similar region of no yield. Away from the fibre end, matrix yielding appears to proceed more easily along the interface of section OB. For an applied load of 206.9 MPa (30 ksi), yielding has progressed approximately one-and-a-half fibre diameters from the fibre end. Further, the plastic front appears to be less warped than for the lower loads.

The shear stress near the interface in the fibre and matrix are reported in Figs. 7 and 8, respectively; A_f, A_m, B_f, B_m refer to the lines of integrating points shown in Fig. 4a. In order to obtain a single measure of shear stress in the longitudinal direction, the Cartesian components τ_{xy}, τ_{yz} were converted to the single value τ_{ry} ,

$$\tau_{ry} = \tau_{xy} \cos \theta + \tau_{yz} \sin \theta \quad (9)$$

Fig. 7: Matrix longitudinal shear stress near the interface.

Fig. 8: Fibre longitudinal shear stress near the interface.

where θ is the angle about the y -axis from the positive x -axis to the line of integrating points in question.

Within the matrix, Fig. 7, the shear stress quickly rises to a peak in the vicinity of the fibre end and then falls with increasing d/r . However, the onset of yielding at the fibre edge restricts the maximum value of this stress so that increasing the applied load merely extends the distance along the fibre for which this stress is a constant. The extent of this plateau in shear stress corresponds to the location of the plastic zone boundary. Further, beyond this plateau, the shear stress is greater than for the corresponding elastic case; in fact, the extent of the plateau is greater than would arise if the elastic shear stress curve was simply chopped at the limiting stress level. This indicates the importance of the shear stress with regard to plastic yielding near the interface. This figure also illustrates that away from the fibre end, the shear stress along section OB is higher, for a given d/r , than along section OA. This supports the observation, in Fig. 6, that the plastic front along section OB leads that of section OA. Further, such behaviour may be expected on the basis of the greater area of matrix for section OB. It is to be noted that the magnitude of the stress peak compares favourably with that reported by Agarwal et al [5,6].

The corresponding curves on the fibre side of the interface are presented in Fig. 8. Although no limiting value and plateau of shear stress is observed, the maxima near the fibre end are less than would be expected had matrix yielding been prohibited; the geometric singularity of the fibre edge causes some difficulty with regard to resolution of the internal stresses in the region $d/r < 0.2$. This is due to the spreading plastic zones near the interface. However, beyond a certain distance from the fibre end, the shear stress is higher than for the equivalent elastic case. Further, there is a discontinuity, located slightly behind the plastic front in the adjacent matrix, in these shear stress curves. Thus the yielded matrix applies an almost constant shear stress at the interface and increases the shear stress in the remaining elastic matrix. These effects influence the fibre stress state near the interface.

The axial stress (σ_x) near the fibre axis (line C in Fig. 4) and in the matrix near the interface is illustrated in Figs. 9 and 10. These curves are markedly different from those presented by Agarwal et al [5,6]. They reflect the importance of the high triaxial stress state near, and the mechanism of normal load transfer through, the fibre end and the state of shear stress at the interface.

Fig. 9: Longitudinal stress near fibre axis.

Fig. 10: Matrix axial stress near the interface.

The normal stress component σ_y near the fibre axis, Fig. 9, falls slightly in the matrix when approaching the fibre end. This fall becomes more pronounced as the applied load is increased past the initial composite yield stress. Further, the matrix stress is less than would be expected for the corresponding elastic case. Within the fibre, a minimum is observed in the region $d/r \approx 0.5$. Thereafter the axial stress increases to a limiting value within approximately two fibre diameters. Both the constant value and the required distance to achieve this stress increase with increasing composite load. To the extent to which the present analysis proceeded, no asymptotic limit was observed for the fibre axial stress with increasing load. This is in stark contrast to the results obtained by Agarwal et al [5,6]. Further, for loads beyond the composite elastic limit, the maximum axial stress (at the fibre centre) is slightly greater than would be observed for the corresponding elastic case. This difference increases with increasing load and is due to the higher shear stresses at the interface. Thus matrix yielding transfers a greater load-carrying role to the fibre, resulting in the tensile stress-strain curve of Fig. 5a.

Fig. 10 presents the axial stress within the matrix near the interface; previous comments regarding resolution of the stress distribution near the fibre edge are also applicable to this case. As with the above case, a high axial stress can be supported in the end gap region due to the triaxial stress state. This stress, however, is below that for the equivalent elastic case. Near the fibre end, a dramatic drop is observed and the axial stress becomes negligible a short distance along the interface. This observation is compatible with the shear stress curves of Fig. 7. With increasing load, the limit to shear stress in the yielded matrix implies an increase in the normal stress components. However, this increase is small compared to the stress in the end gap region. This effect was also observed by Agarwal et al [5,6]. A higher axial load is observed along the line B_m as compared to A_m , and this is consistent with the above argument.

Fig. 11: Discretization geometry for short-fibre composite with non-linear interface.

Fig. 12a: Effect of interfacial failure on stress-strain behaviour.

Fig. 12b: Effect of interfacial failure on longitudinal Poisson ratio.

Load Increment	Number of Iterations	$\tilde{\sigma}_y$ MPa	(ksi)	$\tilde{\epsilon}_y$ %	ν_{LT}
1	1	20.69	(3.000)	0.0159	0.4128
2	2	21.03	(3.050)	0.0162	0.4128
3	3	21.21	(3.075)	0.0163	0.4128
4	5	31.03	(4.500)	0.0240	0.4128
5	6	48.27	(7.000)	0.0374	0.4130
6	17	96.55	(14.000)	0.0757	0.4135
7	3	118.51	(17.185)	0.0930	0.4133
	3			0.0947	0.4117
	3			0.0979	0.4076
	7			0.1042	0.4022
	14			0.1124	0.3983
	20			0.1202	0.3955
	20			0.1260	0.3938

TABLE 2: NON-LINEAR RESPONSE OF SHORT-FIBRE COMPOSITE DUE TO INTERFACIAL FAILURE

DEBONDING EXAMPLE

The problem to be considered is that of interfacial failure for an otherwise elastic short-fibre composite. This problem was devised on the basis of the work of Owen and Lyness [7]. Although these authors also employed the initial stress method, they were unable to obtain convergence even for an applied load just sufficient to initiate slippage. This is not surprising due to the high stress concentrations, especially of the interfacial shear stress, observed in single-fibre models [17]. In the case of elasto-plastic analysis, the inclusion of neighbouring fibres limits the spread of the plastic zones [4] as was observed in the preceding example. It would appear reasonable to expect similar retardation effects in the case of interfacial failure.

The assumed composite geometry is illustrated in Fig. 11 together with the discretization employing 65 solid and 19 interface elements. The relevant composite dimensions are the fibre aspect ratio of 12 and the nearest-neighbour separation of 3 and 1 fibre-diameters in the longitudinal and transverse directions, respectively. This corresponds to a filament volume of 15.7%. The constituent properties were taken as follows:

	<u>Fibre</u>	<u>Matrix</u>
Poisson Ratio	0.10	0.45
Young's Modulus (MPa)	413.78×10^3	82.76×10^3
(psi)	(60.00×10^6)	(12.00×10^6)
	<u>Interface</u>	
Shear Modulus (MPa)	108.34×10^3	
(psi)	(15.71×10^6)	
Tensile Modulus (MPa)	248.27×10^3	
(psi)	(36.00×10^6)	
Maximum Shear Stress $\bar{\tau}_m'$ (MPa)	10.34	
(ksi)	(1.50)	
Residual Shear Stress $\bar{\tau}_r'$ (MPa)	8.28	
(ksi)	(1.20)	
Delamination Criterion ϵ_p'	0.001	

The elastic properties of the interface were calculated from the mixtures relation and assuming equal contributions from the matrix and the fibre. Owen and Lyness [7], suggest this to be a reasonable assumption for practical fibres having a rough surface. For interfacial shear failure, the steady slippage mechanism is assumed with no consideration given to friction.

The composite response to longitudinal load is reported in Fig. 12 and Table 2; RTEST = 10^{-6} for load increments 2 and 3, 10^{-5} for load increment 4, and 10^{-4} thereafter. The composite elastic modulus and initial failure load were calculated to be 129.86×10^3 MPa (18.83×10^6 psi) and ≈ 20.96 MPa (≈ 3.04 ksi) respectively.

Initial failure of the interface was due to slippage at the fibre edge of section OB, Fig. 11a. This reflects the higher interfacial shear stresses for the plane section with greater matrix area; this observation is consistent with the results of the preceding study. Slippage then proceeded around the fibre edge before progressing along the fibre length. Observation of this phenomenon required a convergence test of 10^{-6} for load increments 2 and 3. Thereafter, RTEST was changed as indicated above. Examination of the interfacial shear stresses suggests section OB retains the leading edge of the slippage front. With an applied load of 96.55 MPa (14 ksi), approximately 40% of the cylindrical interface has failed by the slippage mechanism. The progress of this failure is only mildly reflected in the macroscopic composite response, Fig. 12. The stress-strain curve exhibits a slight departure from linearity while a slight rise is observed for the longitudinal Poisson ratio.

Application of the last load increment resulted in catastrophic failure of the entire interface due to delamination at the fibre end. This was initiated at the

Fig. 13: Interfacial shear stress along fibre surface.

Fig. 14: Interfacial normal strain along fibre surface.

Fig. 15: Normalized axial stress near fibre axis.

Fig. 16: Interfacial separation at fibre end.

fibre edge during the second iteration and complete debonding of the fibre end was achieved by the seventh iteration. Thereafter, the remaining intact interface failed in shear although this was by no means a rapid process as indicated in Table 2. The breakdown of the interface is, of course, reflected in the composite longitudinal properties, Fig. 12. In the case of the longitudinal Poisson ratio, a sharp fall was recorded.

Figs. 13 and 14 illustrate the shear stress and normal strain state along the interface in the region of plane OA (line I in Fig. 11a). The axial stress (σ_y) near the fibre axis (line C in Fig. 11a) is reported in Fig. 15. In these figures, curves designated C4, C5 and C7 correspond to the fourth, fifth and seventh stage of the last load increment in Table 2.

As slippage proceeds, a shear stress peak travels down the interface from the fibre end as observed by Owen and Lyness [7], Fig. 13. This is due to the re-distribution of load from failed regions to the adjacent intact interface, thus facilitating further slippage. Providing no delamination has occurred, this stress wave may be arrested and so allow further loading of the composite structure.

Away from the fibre end, but in the vicinity of the slipped region, the axial load supported by the fibre falls, Fig. 15, as compared to the equivalent elastic case. This bears some similarity to the preceding elasto-plastic example and may, in fact, be expected on the basis of the steady slippage mechanism; the use of a non-zero residual shear stress is analogous to the limiting longitudinal shear stress and subsequent plateau region of Fig. 7. Near the fibre end and in the matrix along this axis, an increase in the σ_y component is apparent. This is in contrast to the elasto-plastic example and is associated with the prohibition of matrix yielding. Further, this implies a greater emphasis to direct load transfer through the fibre end and so increases the possibility of delamination in this region.

Delamination at the fibre end leads to a loss of all stress supported in this region. Since interfacial shear is now the only mechanism available to transfer load from the matrix to the fibre, the interface condition may become critical and so lead to total failure of the composite system as observed in the present study. As shear failure accelerates along the interface, Fig. 13, the axial stress falls within the fibre, Fig. 15. During this process, the fibre retracts into the matrix as indicated by the nodal displacements at the fibre end, Fig. 16 ($\delta_y \equiv v$); curves 1 to 4 refer to the nodal positions illustrated in Fig. 11b.

The possibility of frictional assistance for slip arrest is presented in Fig. 14. The normal strain along the interface is compressive at all stages of composite loading. As slippage progresses, this strain component falls in the vicinity of the slipped interface but increases towards the fibre centre. Further, following catastrophic failure, these differences are more marked as observed during the iterative process.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

A three-dimensional finite element technique is presented for the prediction of the uniaxial longitudinal mechanical behaviour of an aligned short-fibre composite. The essential features of this method are the use of isoparametric elements with quadratic displacement fields to model the material regions and the constraint formulation of the composite problem boundary conditions. For non-linear analysis, an elasto-plastic model is adopted for the solid components and a debonding model is proposed for the fibre-matrix interface. The initial stress method is employed for the non-linear solution scheme.

Two examples are selected from the literature in order to demonstrate the three-dimensional analysis. For both examples, the local non-linear behaviour (matrix yielding/interfacial slippage) propagates more readily along the fibre surface associated with the included matrix. However, the influence of the fibre end and of the neighbouring fibres on the subsequent stress re-distribution arrests the progress of these non-linear regions so that higher loads may be applied to the

composite structure. Further, the non-linear behaviour is reflected in the composite longitudinal Poisson ratio. Although complete failure of the interface was eventually obtained for the debonding example, the controlling mechanism was delamination at the fibre end. This situation is in contrast to that reported for single-fibre studies. For the elasto-plastic example, the predicted composite stress-strain curve did not exhibit any dramatic levelling as suggested by Agarwal et al [5,6]. This difference is associated with the presence of high triaxial stresses in the matrix region between collinear fibres. These results demonstrate the differences to be observed between a fully three-dimensional finite element analysis of multi-array short-fibre composites as compared to two-dimensional treatments.

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